

THE CONCEPT OF "COMMUNICATION" AND ITS IMPORTANCE IN THE SYSTEM OF INTERPERSONAL RELATIONS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18712288>

The phenomenon of "communication" is considered an integral part of the system of interpersonal relations, it is one of the constant conditions for the conduct of group and collective relations. According to E.N. Reznikov, there are three types of interpersonal communication [1] :

imperative communication - this type of communication is widely used to exercise control over the behavior, attitude and thoughts of the interlocutors, to force the interlocutor to take certain actions or decisions. In this type of communication, one of the interlocutors acts as a passive object or victim. An example of this is the relationship between a manager and an employee;

Manipulative communication - the essence of such communication is that it involves covert influence in order to achieve the intentions of the communication partner. That is, many of the successful qualities of the interlocutors are adopted. As an example of this situation, D. Carnegie's ideas about communication can be cited as an example. Manipulative communication style has become very popular in the field of propaganda [2] ;

Dialogic communication is a process of equal interaction between subject and subject, which is aimed at mutual cooperation and self-knowledge of the interlocutors. Such communication is possible only if a number of rules of relations are observed [3] .

These forms of communication are considered to be specific means of communication, through which non-verbal elements of information acquisition are provided. The process of reflection also plays an important role in interpersonal relationships, through which people evaluate each other's behavior and actions, as well as their self-understanding. It should be noted that the successful work of military personnel largely depends on the management competence of commanders, in which the criteria for effective communication with subordinates play an important role. Researcher MI Marin is a scientist who has conducted extensive research on this issue. In his opinion, commanders and leaders should have the following competencies for successful communication [4]

ability to take into account communication situations;

be able to perceive the socio-psychological reasons for military service;

taking into account the military and professional achievements of military personnel, their value system, professional experience, and the traditions and norms of their community [5] ;

anticipating psychological barriers to communication and taking into account subsequent situations, i.e. motivational, emotional, intellectual, volitional capabilities, etc.;

Good knowledge of the causes of service conflicts and ways to resolve them.

Communication is a necessary form of relationship between people in joint activities. In the process of communication, the inner world of one person is transferred to another person or his spiritual world is enriched. Therefore, communication is also considered a means of exchanging needs between people in a spiritual sense.

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